

ART

UDC: 069

Babayeva S.R.*PhD in Art**Azerbaijan Tourism and Management University**Baku, Azerbaijan*

ORCID 0000-0003-1372-4852

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889354>**CURATORIAL EXHIBITION AS PART OF THE EXHIBITION ACTIVITIES OF A CULTURAL INSTITUTION****Abstract:**

The article is devoted to the importance of a curatorial exhibition as part of the exhibition activities of a cultural institution. It is indicated that the active involvement of society in art by cultural institutions is carried out mainly through holding various exhibitions. One of the forms of exhibition activities is a curatorial exhibition (and tour).

Using comparative historical analysis and research of extensive literature, the definition and types of curatorship, their place in the organization and conduct of exhibitions are given. Extensive material on holding curatorial exhibitions and tours by leading museums of the world is provided.

Keywords: *curator, museum curator, independent curator, exhibition, tour, museum, gallery, audience.*

Introduction. Over the past few decades, museum exhibition activities have moved from complete static to dynamism, bringing new forms of demonstrating cultural and historical heritage to the stage. Although one of the main goals of the museum is to educate and enlighten the public, it is more than obvious today that few visitors would voluntarily wish to visit these purposeful classical static exhibitions without serious outside incentive. The modern visitor wants to get positive emotions and deep impressions from a dynamic exhibition, which actively and, most importantly, purposefully uses modern information technologies, where the audience actively participates in various seminars and workshops and conducts interesting mutual communication with specialists about the exhibited museum artifacts. Modern technical and innovative achievements help the museum in this, providing the opportunity to transform the exhibition space in accordance with the theme of the exhibition, inviting specialists from other museums, specialized scientists and designers both from their own country and from abroad. Museums are actively using these achievements to optimize the functioning of the system of interaction between the museum exhibition and the audience.

Research part. In exhibition activities, the effectiveness of communication between a museum and its audience is also achieved through the organization of a short-term event held by a cultural institution and dedicated to a specific topic or a work of art. Moreover, this event is held in a specific hall of a museum or gallery, in which a special aesthetic environment is formed, that is, the works of art surrounding visitors create an atmosphere of involvement in the event, enrich perception and make a deep impression from meeting them.

This form of attracting an audience and active interaction with visitors is reflected in such a type of exhibition activity of museums and galleries as curatorial exhibitions (or tours), which began in the 60-70s of the

last century. This period was marked by various experiments with new forms of exhibitions and an active search for more effective ways of introducing society to art. The most important event of that time was the exhibition of the Swiss inventor of curating, Harald Szeemann, who helped to rethink contemporary art. With the exhibition “When Relationships Become Form,” shown in 1969 at the Bernese Kunsthalle, Szeemann brought together a wide range of international artists who were turning to socially interactive forms of work. A thoughtful reading of the exhibition assumed that the viewer’s attention should be directed not only to the exhibited objects, but also to the figure of the exhibition organizer, who conceived this event, constructed its dramaturgy and directed its course in time. The final formation of the institute of curatorial activity took place in the 80s of the last century with the emergence of the first nine-month educational programs dedicated to curatorial activity. In 1987, the Le Magasin Art Centre in Grenoble launched Europe’s first graduate curatorial training programme, l’Ecole du Magasin, which still exists today. At the same time, the Art History/Museology Study Group within the Whitney Independent Study Program was renamed Curatorial and Critical Research. Since then, curatorial practice has become both an academic discipline and an independent profession.

The 90s of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century were accompanied by the active development of the institution of curating, which is directly connected with the rapid spread, first of all, of the exhibition format of the biennial [1, p. 7].

Application of innovative technologies has raised this type of exhibition activity to a new level of development, turning curatorial exhibitions into an important event in the life of art and society.

However, before moving on to the characteristics and features of a curated exhibition (tour), it is necessary to define the term “curator” and his role in the

preparation and holding of the exhibition. The word “curator” comes from the Latin word “*curare*” meaning guardian, trustee, that is, a person who oversees the progress of a certain work or process [2]. In the field of contemporary art, the figure of the curator, as indicated above, acquired special significance in the 80-90s of the last century, when the phenomenon of celebrity curators emerged.

Modern explanatory dictionaries of the English language give the following definition of the term “curator”: 1) a person in charge of a department of a museum or other place where objects of art, science, or from the past are collected, or a person who organizes and arranges a showing of art or other objects of interest (Cambridge Dictionary) [3]; 2) A curator is a person whose job it is to be responsible for objects or works of art in a museum, art gallery, etc. (Oxford Dictionary) [4]; 3) A curator is a person who is responsible for objects or works of art in a museum or art gallery (Collins Dictionary) [5].

The Russian Museum Encyclopedia “Dictionary of Museum Terms” defines a curator (*from the Latin curare – trustee*): 1) an exhibition curator is a person responsible for the implementation of an exhibition project; 2) a curator of contemporary art is an exhibition curator, who is often an active participant, co-author and interpreter of an art project, may be invited or be on the staff of the museum; 3) in Western countries, also the custodian of one of the collections and at the same time the exhibitor (curator) or chief custodian (museum curator) [6].

The Dictionary of Museum Terms defines a curator (trustee, guardian) in a museum as a person who heads the development and implementation of a museum project. Under his leadership, a project (working) group is formed, each member of which is a specialist in a certain field (law, finance, transportation, insurance). Outside specialists (designer, architect) may be invited to join the group. In addition to narrow professional knowledge in the field of museology, project supervision also requires knowledge of management, i.e. project management as a whole [7, p. 85].

Thus, based on the above definitions and the development trend of exhibition activities, the role of curators in the life of a cultural institution, in the dissemination of cultural heritage is extremely high. Museum curators are specialists in a specific subject area related to the mission of their museum, researchers of museum collections, exhibition developers and public custodians of collections.

In today’s rapidly changing world, museums are moving away from being static repositories of artifacts to becoming important centers for dialogue with society, exchange of ideas, and scientific research. In this context, the role of the curator is expanding, intertwined with active interaction with the audience, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the dissemination of important information about history, culture, and art. Thanks to his/her unique understanding of collections, curators are well placed to make connections between works of history and art and contemporary social issues. This is very clearly reflected in the events (curated

exhibitions and tours) that curators themselves run within the museum or gallery.

Despite the fact that a curated exhibition organically exists as one of the types of exhibition activities of a museum and, to a greater extent, an art gallery, the form and conceptual basis of this event differs from a museum exhibition. The peculiarity of a curated exhibition is its theme, focus, and inherent storyline. When creating a project for a proposed exhibition, the curator selects certain works based not only on their significance, but also on the idea, storyline, and completed composition of the event that he has formed.

The practice of holding modern curated exhibitions of works of art by museums and art galleries shows that they are not limited to just demonstrating exhibits and art objects, but include an extensive program to attract the audience to the event, which may consist of thematic lectures, master classes, communication with curators and specialized experts, etc.

At the same time, it is necessary to note here an important feature of curatorial activity, which objectively forms this activity. In the practical life of culture and art there are the two types of curatorship associated with the person’s affiliation with curatorial activity. The first type are curators who are employees of a state cultural institution (museum or gallery), and the second ones are independent curators who carry out their activities on the basis of agreements concluded with cultural and artistic figures to organize exhibitions related to their work or a museum or gallery - to be assisted in holding certain events of the institution.

In the first case, when the curator is a full-time employee of a museum or gallery, all his activities are carried out within the framework of the mission, tasks and work plan of the cultural institution. During the organization and holding of a curatorial exhibition, with all his creative approach, rich experience and brilliant knowledge of the works of art on display, his positive qualities are limited by the need to adhere to the storyline approved by the museum and the multitude of his job responsibilities as one of the leading employees of this institution. The curator’s duties include preserving works of art, researching them and forming collections, as well as organizing exhibitions. Thus, organizing all types of exhibitions, improving permanent exhibitions presupposes a high share of research activities, serious and at the same time original presentation of artistic material. The result of his activities is the formation of a significant museum collection, the development of a single artistic project that reveals the essence and content of the exhibition.

Despite the importance of a curatorial exhibition in a museum, numerous job responsibilities and limited opportunities for independent creative approach in organizing and holding a curatorial exhibition, as a rule, significantly narrow the possibilities of a museum curator to independently hold these events. This circumstance is especially noticeable in the activities of leading museums, which annually plan and hold dozens of large thematic national and international exhibitions, in which all museum curators are actively involved. As a result, the curators of these museums, in addition to directly participating in the organization and holding of

the above-mentioned exhibitions, also provide online support for them (so-called online curatorial tours). On the pages of the museums' social networks, curators post lengthy stories about the exhibitions taking place and provide an interesting selection of thematic information related to a specific exhibit or work of art.

Such are, for example, the curators' corners of the British Museum. Thus, on the British Museum's YouTube channel dedicated to the exhibition "The World of Stonehenge", the museum has posted ten videos, seven of which are about an hour or more long. The first video, entitled "Curator's corner", was posted by the British Museum on February 10, 2022, that is, a week before the start of the exhibition itself. The museum curator provided a brief introduction to the exhibition over the course of seven and a half minutes. It was viewed 189,000 times. The museum posted the next video on February 24, 2022. The video, one hour and two minutes long, was called "Curator's introduction." It detailed the history of the exhibit and provided other information about the event. This video has been viewed 33,000 times. Between March and June 2022, the British Museum posted eight videos, totaling 8 hours and 27 minutes. These videos focused on various aspects of the exhibition. Museum curators introduced the virtual audience to the history and individual exhibits of Stonehenge and provided extensive factual material about the exhibition. These videos have been viewed 698,885 times [8]. This dynamic of curatorial online tours also applies to other exhibitions held by the museum over the past three years (2022-2024).

At the same time, today museums actively use such a type of communication with the audience as curatorial tours. The duration of these tours can take from one hour to several days, depending on the intensity and content of the tour program. Thus, the program of one of the many curatorial tours of the British Museum "Around the World in 90 Minutes" involves getting acquainted with a number of the most famous exhibits exhibited in various halls of the museum. During the tour, the curator provides detailed information about each exhibit, answers questions of interest to visitors [9].

The Louvre Museum organizes various thematic curatorial tours as one of its areas of work with the audience. One of these curatorial tours is the "Private Tour of the Louvre" lasting three hours. On this three-hour tour of the Louvre, visitors are accompanied by a curator who is an art historian. During the tour, the curator provides detailed information about the Louvre Museum's most visited collection of works of art in the world, as well as organizes discussions on certain exhibits and answers visitors' questions [10].

The Metropolitan Museum of Art offers an extensive program of curatorial tours for its audience. The tour program is intended to attract all categories of society and is designed for both adults and children. The topics cover historical artifacts, works of culture and art. In particular, the curatorial tour program "Met Expert Talks" is intended to introduce visitors to works of art and, receive positive impressions from it, through active mutual communication with museum experts, including curators, restorers, scientists and researchers.

The museum offers a varied curatorial program of children's tours. Thus, the program of one of the children's tours "How did they do it?" involves a program of direct participation of children through the use of tools and materials in learning the technique of creating works of art. During the tour, a curator, teacher or restorer popularly talks about the features of creating certain works of art. Another children's tour, "Start with Art at The Met/Start with Art and Music" engages children in the world of history, culture, and art through sharing ideas, storytelling, sketching, singing, and other gallery activities that bring the artworks to life [11]. Similar curatorial tours are also organized by other leading museums around the world.

Along with curatorial tours, museums also host full-fledged curatorial exhibitions. One such curatorial exhibition was the one held at the Audian Art Museum in Cleveland, Ohio, from February to May 2024, organized by the trio of curators Kiriko Watanabe, Gail and Stephen A. Jarislowsky. The exhibition, "Manabu Ikeda: Flowers from the Wreckage" featured Ikeda's meticulously detailed pen-and-ink drawings, filled with startling imagery. The viewer was offered an impressive interactive communication with the content of the exhibition, while discovering a certain artistic text, a unique narrative, unfolding as they delved deeper into it. At the same time, the viewer was free in individual interpretation, personal understanding. As a result, such multifaceted communication with art turned from an ordinary visit to the exhibition into a memorable event [12].

A curated exhibition as an event of active interaction with the audience is widely used by art galleries in various countries. Such an exhibition is one of the main types of demonstration of works of art available in the gallery. Due to this, such an exhibition is not limited by strict program frameworks. It is usually characterized by the creativity of the curatorial approach to the organization and holding of this event, the depth of thematic content, information content and active communication with the audience.

These include curated exhibitions at the National Gallery Singapore, such as the exhibition "Tropical: Stories from Southeast Asia and Latin America" held in February 2024 by two curators of the gallery, Teo Hui Min and Qingyi Lim. The exhibition featured over 200 works of art created by artists from these regions of the world. It was the first large-scale exhibition in the world to take a comparative approach between the artistic styles and expressions of Southeast Asia and Latin America [13].

Curatorial exhibitions held by the State Tretyakov Gallery in Moscow are interesting in terms of the subject matter and significance of the works of art exhibited. An example of such an event is the curatorial tour of the exhibition "Heroes and Contemporaries of the Silver Age", held from December 2023 to June 2024. The exhibition featured works by famous artists - symbols of the "Silver Age" Mikhail Vrubel, Valentin Serov, Viktor Borisov-Musatov, as well as works by artists from the "World of Art" association, "Blue Rose" and masters of other movements who contributed to the art of the "Silver Age" [14]. This practice of

holding curated exhibitions is widely used by art galleries in various countries.

Unlike museum curators, independent curators are not limited by any framework of job responsibilities. In their work, they are free to choose to collaborate with a particular cultural institution, group or individual artist, sculptor in organizing and holding an exhibition. At the same time, their work, in addition to its creative focus, is also quite commercial in nature. Working on a commercial basis, independent curators collaborate with national and private galleries to organize and hold various exhibitions. They are invited as specialists to organize museum permanent and traveling exhibitions, international festivals and biennials, and also create their own works of curatorial art.

The work of famous curators in organizing numerous cultural events is highly valued by cultural institutions (museums, galleries), private collectors of art and sculpture rarities, and art figures. Famous curators create masterpieces of exhibition art – world-renowned curatorial exhibitions, biennials, exhibitions of private collections, and other events.

Known for its coverage of various national and international art events and for publishing extensive articles on the subject, Artland Magazine has posted on its website a list of ten influential curators shaping the contemporary art world [15].

First on this list is Hans Ulrich Obrist, co-director of the Serpentine Gallery in London. In his curatorial project “Agency of Unrealized Projects,” he has drawn the attention of a wider audience to projects those artists, who for one reason or another, had been unable to realize. Another initiative of H.U. Obrist is the curated exhibition *Do It*, which began in Paris in 1993 as a conversation between Obrist and the artists Christian Boltanski and Bertrand Lavier. Obrist was concerned with how exhibition formats could be made more flexible and open. To this end, he invited 12 artists to submit their ideas for organizing exhibitions of works of art created by past generations of artists and by contemporary artists anywhere in the world. More than 20 years after the initial conversation, “*Do It*” is now presented in at least 50 different locations in more than ten countries around the world. Each “*Do It*” exhibition is unique, site-specific, as it engages the local community in dialogue, while remaining global in its ever-expanding repertoire [16].

Next on the list is independent curator Caroline Christov-Bakargiev. Under her direction, the acclaimed 2012 curatorial exhibition “*Documenta 13*” showcased works by contemporary artists and works of art and artefacts from the past. It was one of the most significant exhibitions in the art world, bringing together art and culture to create a close relationship with the audience [17].

Catherine Morris, a curator at the Elizabeth A. Sackler Center for Feminist Art at the Brooklyn Museum, organized and curated a series of exhibitions titled “*A Year of Yes: Reimagining Feminism at the Brooklyn Museum*” in 2016-2017. The series of exhibitions presented the history of feminism and feminist art, as well as showcased contemporary artistic practices and new thought leadership [18]. In addition, she

had held other curatorial exhibitions of works related to the work of various female artists.

In addition to the above curators, the magazine names Massimiliano Gioni, who organically combines the works of young and old artists, as well as different artistic trends, when holding exhibitions. Gioni, as the director of the Venice Biennale in 2013, and under his curatorship, the exhibition “*The Encyclopedic Palace*” was held. The exhibition presented works by contemporary artists, as well as works of art from the past. In addition, works by little-known artists were exhibited, which were given an incentive for further creativity [19].

The ten influential curators include Helen Molesworth, chief curator of the Museum of Contemporary Art, Los Angeles; RoseLee Goldberg, founding director and curator of Performa, a leading organization dedicated to live performance in the arts of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries; Lowry Stokes Sims, independent curator and Curator Emeritus of the Museum of Arts and Design, New York; Hamza Walker, executive director of LAXART; Thelma Golden, director and chief curator of the Studio Museum in Harlem, New York; and the late Okwui Enwezor (1963-2019), former director of the Haus der Kunst, Munich.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the above and despite the general focus of various exhibitions, which consist of demonstrating works of art, the role and place of a museum curator in this event differs significantly from the role and place of an independent curator. When organizing and holding exhibitions, the curator of a cultural institution is limited by the relevant management and scientific information concerning the objects on display. As a result, there is little room for independence and creativity in holding an exhibition.

On the contrary, an independent curator is free to choose the theme of the exhibition, the method and form of the author's demonstration of exhibits, which gives originality to the event and attracts the audience. However, modern transformations occurring in society are radically changing the paradigm of museum work. Leading museums, striving to meet the modern demands of the audience, are moving away from the classical forms of demonstrating their collections and are beginning to pay significant attention to such forms of activity as curatorial exhibitions and tours. As a result, they are actively attracting independent curators to cooperation, and also creating conditions for the creative approach of museum curators in organizing and holding exhibitions.

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